

The Corelation of Body Mass Indeks and Menstrual Periode In Teenagers

Ni Wayan Sukma Adnyani*, Ni Made Sri Diantini, Chania Pradnyawati Made

Politeknik Kesehatan Kartini Bali

*Corresponding email: Ni Wayan Sukma Adnyani. sukmaadnyani@gmail.com

Abstract

Introduction: Body Mass Index (BMI) is used to determine a person's nutritional status determined by measuring weight and height in kg/m^2 . High or low Body Mass Index (BMI) can cause disturbances in the duration and amount of menstrual blood. **Purpose:** This study aims to determine the relationship between body mass index and the length of menstruation in adolescent girls at SMA Negeri 1 Susut Bangli. **Methods:** This type of research is correlation analytic with a cross sectional approach. The population in this study were all students of class X at SMA Negeri 1 Susut Bangli, with a sample size of 128 respondents. Analysis of the selected data using the Kolmogorov/Smirnov test with a technique using a questionnaire. The data analysis technique for the relationship between body mass index in adolescent girls is by calculating the percentage (%) of correct answers. **Results:** a minimum BMI value of 14.5 and a maximum value of 31.5 with a median value of 19.0. a minimum of 3 days and a maximum value of 9 days with a median value of 6 days. The results of the data analysis showed a p value of 0.000 and the value of the strength of $\rho = 0.550$. **Conclusions:** The conclusion is that there is a relationship between body mass index and the length of menstruation in adolescent girls at SMA Negeri 1 Susut Bangli. Respondents can find out BMI so they can keep BMI normal.

Keywords: Body Mass Index, Menstruation Length, Adolescent Girls

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a dynamic phase of development in an individual's life. It is a transitional period from childhood to adulthood, characterized by accelerated physical, mental, emotional, and social development occurring in the second decade of life (Pardede, 2018). Adolescence marks the transition between childhood and adulthood, highlighted by puberty. In adolescent girls, puberty involves sexual maturation, egg maturation, and estrogen production, leading to the onset of menstruation, known as menarche. Menstruation is periodic and cyclic bleeding from the uterus (Pangemanan, 2017).

Menstruation is a natural process experienced by women. Normal menstruation lasts between 3 to 7 days. Menstruation lasting less than 3 days is

termed hypomenorrhea, while menstruation lasting more than 7 days is termed hypermenorrhea (Pangemanan, 2017). Variations in menstruation duration among women are due to imbalances in hormones such as LH, FSH, estrogen, and progesterone, nutritional status, stress, or disease. Inadequate or excessive nutrition can lead to nutritional imbalances, potentially causing disruptions in menstrual duration (Novita, 2018). Such issues are often encountered by adolescents, particularly in urban areas.

Nutritional status can be assessed through Body Mass Index (BMI). BMI is a parameter established by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a ratio of body weight to the square of height. BMI is determined by measuring weight and height separately and then dividing the weight by the square of height to obtain

the BMI value in kg/m². High or low BMI can affect the duration and volume of menstrual bleeding (Novita, 2018). Research indicates that six respondents with a BMI categorized as obese had abnormal menstruation lasting more than 7 days, while 20 respondents with a BMI categorized as underweight had abnormal menstruation lasting less than 3 days (Rahmawati, 2014).

Based on a preliminary study conducted in February and March 2022 at SMA Negeri 1 Susut Bangli, which involved measuring the weight and height of 163 female students from class X to determine their BMI, it was found that menstruation occurs monthly in all women who have reached adolescence. Prolonged menstruation can lead to blood loss. Nutritional factors are one of the factors affecting the duration of menstruation in adolescents. Currently, many adolescents engage in low physical activity, frequent dieting, consume fast food, and skip breakfast. This is particularly prevalent in urban areas, making it important to research. The aim of this study is to determine the relationship between Body Mass Index and menstrual duration in tenth-grade adolescent girls.

METHODS

This study is a correlational research with a Cross-Sectional design. The research was conducted at SMA Negeri 1 Susut Bangli. This location was chosen because SMA Negeri 1 Susut Bangli has 160 female students in grade X. The researcher

selected grade X as most of the students in this grade have started menstruating. Sampling was carried out using the Slovin technique and based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. The sampling technique used in this study is Proportional Random Sampling through a lottery method. In random sampling, each class in the population has a chance to be selected as a sample (Notoatmodjo, 2019). Thus, a sample size of 128 respondents was obtained. Data collection was carried out using a structured questionnaire related to menstrual duration, and tools to measure body weight and height to determine Body Mass Index (BMI). BMI calculation was done by dividing the weight in kilograms by the square of height in meters. Univariate analysis was performed using the frequency of both variables and determining the mean, median, minimum value, maximum value, and standard deviation. Bivariate analysis used Spearman Rank. Data are considered significant if $p < 0.05$ (Notoatmodjo, 2010).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the questionnaire completed at SMA Negeri 1 Susut are as follows:

a. Body Mass Index (BMI) of Respondents

Based on the measurements of weight and height conducted at SMA Negeri 1 Susut, the BMI of respondents is as follows:

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents by Body Mass Index

Characteristics	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage (%)
Underweight < 18,5	50	39,1
Normal 18,5 – 24,9	67	52,3
Overweight >25,0– 27,0	11	8,8
Total	128	100

BMI is a value comparing body weight in kilograms to height in square meters. The research data shows that the majority of respondents have a BMI in the

normal category (18.5 – 24.9), with 67 individuals (52.3%). The number of respondents with a BMI less than 18.5 is 50 (39.1%), and those with a BMI greater

than 24.9 is 11 respondents (8.6%). The median BMI calculated for the female students at SMA Negeri 1 Susut is 19.0, which falls within the normal category.

b. Duration of Menstruation of Respondents

Table 2 Characteristics of Respondents by Duration of Menstruation

Characteristics	Number of Respondents (f)	Percentage (%)
< 3 Days	0	0
3- 7 Days	95	74,2
>7 Days	33	25,8
Total	128	100

Adolescent girls, in the process of growth and development, will experience the menstrual phase. The duration of menstruation is the period from the first day of menstruation until the bleeding stops. Data from the research conducted at SMA Negeri 1 Susut show that most of the female students have a normal menstruation duration (3-7 days), with 95 respondents (74.2%) experiencing this duration, and 33 respondents (25.8%) having a menstruation duration longer

Based on the results from the completed questionnaires at SMA Negeri 1 Susut, the duration of menstruation for respondents is as follows:

than 7 days. The median value obtained from the interviews on menstruation duration at SMA Negeri 1 Susut is 6 days, which falls within the normal range.

c. Relationship Between Body Mass Index and Duration of Menstruation

Based on the research conducted at SMA Negeri 1 Susut on the relationship between body mass index (BMI) and the duration of menstruation, the following results were obtained:

Table 3. Hubungan Indeks Massa Tubuh dengan Lama Menstrusi

Variable	Minimum	Maximum	Median	R	P
BMI	14,5	31,5	19,0	0,550	0,000
Duration of Menstruation	3	9	6		

Based on the table above, the data analysis on the relationship between Body Mass Index (BMI) and menstrual duration, using the Spearman Rank test, yielded a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. The correlation coefficient was $r = 0.550$ (strong correlation) with a positive direction. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. This result indicates a relationship between BMI and menstrual duration among adolescent girls at SMA Negeri 1 Susut in 2022. This study shows that BMI can affect the duration of menstruation.

The study results show that among 67 respondents with a normal BMI (18.5 – 24.9), 55 (82%) had normal menstrual duration (3-7 days), and 12 (17.9%) had abnormal menstrual duration (>7 days). Among 61 respondents with an abnormal BMI, those with BMI less than 18.5 included 50 respondents, with 38 (76%) having normal menstrual duration (3-7 days) and 12 (24%) having abnormal menstrual duration (>7 days). Those with BMI greater than 24.9 included 11 respondents, with 2 (18.2%) having normal menstrual duration (3-7 days) and 9 (81.8%) having abnormal menstrual duration (>7 days).

These results are supported by research conducted by Rahmawati (2019), which found a relationship between BMI and menstrual duration. In that study, 6 respondents with an obese BMI category had 83.3% with abnormal menstrual duration and 16.7% with normal menstrual duration. There were 20 respondents with an underweight BMI category, with 20% having abnormal menstrual duration and 80% having normal menstrual duration. These results align with research by Osayande (2019), which found that adolescent girls with higher BMI experienced a significant extension of menstrual duration compared to those with normal body weight. This may occur because women with a higher BMI have increased aromatization of androgens into estrogen, leading to higher estrogen levels. Women with a low BMI or malnutrition experience shorter menstrual bleeding or less blood flow, potentially due to insufficient estrogen levels, which affects endometrial fertility.

High estrogen levels provide negative feedback on GnRH secretion, leading to decreased FSH secretion and preventing follicle growth. This can cause irregular bleeding, which is associated with hormonal imbalance and anovulation (failure to ovulate). Without proper secretion, proliferation and vascularization do not occur. When ovulation does not happen, the endometrium breaks down randomly and blood vessels open, leading to excessive and prolonged uterine bleeding (Rahmawati, 2019).

CONCLUSION

Based on the research conducted on the relationship between Body Mass Index (BMI) and menstrual duration among adolescent girls at SMA Negeri 1 Susut in 2022, it can be concluded that there is a relationship between BMI and menstrual duration among grade X female students. Most of the adolescent girls with a BMI in

the normal category (18.5 – 24.9) also had normal menstrual duration (3-7 days).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The researcher extends gratitude to all those who made this research possible. Special thanks go to SMA Negeri 1 Susut in Bangli District and the grade X students, the Kartini Bali Health Polytechnic institution, and the research colleagues who participated in the execution of this study.

REFERENCES

1. Anindita, P., Darwin, E., Afriwardi. 2016. Hubungan Aktivitas Fisik Harian dengan Gangguan Menstruasi pada Mahasiswa Fakultas Kedokteran Universitas Andalas. *Jurnal Kesehatan Andalas*. Vol.4(8). Tersedia dalam <http://http://jurnal.fk.unand.ac.id>. Diakses tanggal 21 mei 2019
2. Azizah. 2013. Kebahagiaan Dan Permasalahan Di Usia Remaja, *Jurnal Bimbingan Konseling islam*. Vol.4(2), pp. 295–316. tersedia dalam journal.stainkudus.ac.id/index.php/konseling/article/download/1008/921. diakses tanggal 12 februari 2019.
3. Cahyaning, F. 2018. Gambaran Lama Haid. *Jurnal Jurusan Keperawatan Fakultas Ilmu Kesehatan Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta*. tersedia dalam [Http://Eprints.Ums.Ac.Id/59731/17/Naskah%20publikasi%20ii.Pdf](http://Eprints.Ums.Ac.Id/59731/17/Naskah%20publikasi%20ii.Pdf). diakses tanggal 12 februari 2019
4. Chairiyah, H., Syamsuddin, H., Tunggal, T. 2018. Hubungan Tingkat Stres Denan Siklus Menstruasi pada Siswi Pondok Pesantren An-Najah Cindai Alus Martapura. *Jurnal jurusan Kebidanan Poltekkes Kemenkes Banjarmasin*. tersedia dalam www.ejurnalskalakesehatan-poltekkesbjm.com. diakses tanggal 20 maret 2019.

5. Hidayat, A. 2012. Uji Pearson Product Moment dan Asumsi Klasik. *Statistikian*. 1 Juli. tersedia dalam <https://www.statistikian.com/2012/07/pearson-dan-asumsi-klasik.html/amp>. diakses tanggal 3 April 2019.
6. Kementerian Kesehatan RI. 2010. *Profil Kesehatan Indonesia*. tersedia dalam <http://www.depkes.go.id/resources/pusdatin/profil/kesehatanindonesia/profil-kesehatan-indonesia-2010.pdf>. diakses tanggal 22 februari 2019.
7. 2013. *Profil Kesehatan Indonesia*. tersedia dalam <http://www.depkes.go.id/resources/pusdatin/profil/kesehatanindonesia/profil-kesehatan-indonesia-2013.pdf>. diakses tanggal 18 maret 2019.
8. 2015. *Infodatin Reproduksi Remaja, Pusat Informasi Kementerian Kesehatan RI*, P.8. Doi: 24427659. tersedia dalam [Http://Www.Depkes.Go.Id/Resource/Download/Pusdatin/Infodatin/Infodatin reproduksi remaja.Pdf](Http://Www.Depkes.Go.Id/Resource/Download/Pusdatin/Infodatin/Infodatin%20reproduksi%20remaja.Pdf). diakses tanggal 20 februari 2019.
9. 2019. Menkes: *remaja indonesia harus sehat, Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia*, pp. 2–3 tersedia dalam <http://www.depkes.go.id/pdf18051600001>. diakses tanggal 22 februari 2019 .
10. Kundre, R., Felicia., & Hutagaol, E. (2015). Hubungan Sttus Gizi dengan Siklus Mentrulasi pada Remaja Putri di PSIK FK UNSRAT MANADO. *ejournal Keperawata Volume 3*. tersedia dalam <https://ejournal.unsrat.ac.id/index.php/jkp/article/view/6694>
11. Lucy, H. 2016. *Uji Normalitas Data Kesehatan Menggunakan SPSS*. Yogyakarta :Poltekkes Jogja Pres [http://eprints.poltekkesjogja.ac.id/46/1/Buku New Statistik.pdf](http://eprints.poltekkesjogja.ac.id/46/1/Buku%20New%20Statistik.pdf)
12. Notoatmodjo. 2010. *Metodologi Penelitian Kesehatan*. Jakarta : Rineka Medika.
13. Novita, R. 2018. Hubungan Status Gizi Dengan Gangguan Menstruasi Pada Remaja Putri Di SMA Al-Azhar Surabaya. Vol. 2(2) pp. 172–181. tersedia dalam <Https://E-Journal.Unair.Ac.Id/AMNT/Article/View/7351>. diakses tanggal 22 februari 2019.
14. Nurcahyo, F. 2011. Kaitan Antara Obesitas Dan Aktivitas Fisik. Yogyakarta: Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta. *Medikora* Vol. VII, (1), pp. 87 – 96. trsedia dalam <https://journal.uny.ac.id>. diakses tanggal 18 maret 2018
15. Osayande, S.I., Ozoene, J.O., Body Mass Index Influences The Age at Menarche and Duration of Menstrual Cycle. *America Jurnal of Health*. tersedia dalam <http://www.sciencepublishinggroup.com/j/ajhr>.
16. Pangemanan. 2017. Hubungan Antara Stres Dan Pola Siklus Menstruasi Pada Mahasiswa Kepaniteraan Klinik Madya (Co-Assistant). *Jurnal E-Biomedik (Ebm)*, 5(1). tersedia dalam <Https://Media.Neliti.Com/Media/Publications/66824-ID-Hubungan-Antara-Stres-Dan-Pola-Siklus-Me.Pdf>. diakses tanggal 22 februari 2019.
17. Pradana, A. 2014. Hubungan Antara Indeks Massa Tubuh (IMT) dengan Nilai Lemak Viseral. *Jurnal Media Medika Muda Fakultas Kedokteran, universitas Diponegoro..* tersedia dalam <http://portalgaruda.org> diakses tanggal 18 maret 2019
18. Rahmawati, A. 2014. Hubunga Indeks Massa Tubuh Dengan Lama Menstruasi Mahasiswa DIII Kebidanan FK UNS. tersedia dalam <prosiding5.pdf> diakses tanggal 23 februsri 2019.

19. Pujiai., Arneliwati., Rahmalia, S. 2015. Hubungan Antara Perilaku Makan Dengan Status Gizi Pada Remaja Putri. Vol.2(2). tersedia dalam <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/187639-ID-hubungan-antara-perilaku-makan-dengan-st.pdf>. diakses tanggal 18 maret 2019.
20. Simbolon, P., Sukohar, A., Ariwibowo, C., Susianti. 2016. Hubungan Indeks Massa Tubuh dengan Lama Siklus Menstruasi pada Mahasiswi Angkatan 2016 Fakultas Kedokteran Universitas Lampung. *Jurnal Majority*. Vol.7(2). tersedia dalam fdiakses tanggal 2 april 2019.
21. Sinaga, E., Saribanon, N., Nailus, S.S., Salamah, N., Andani, Y.M., Trisnamiati, A., Lorita, S. 2017. *Manajemen Kesehatan Menstruasi*, Universitas Nasional IWWASH Global One
22. Supariasa, I. D. N., Bakri, B. dan Fajar, I. 2018 *Penilaian Status Gizi*. Jakarta: Penerbit Buku Kedokteran EGC.
23. Sugiyono.2010. *Metode Penelitian Pendidika Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*. Bandung : CV Alfa Beta.